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DELVING INTO THE DEPTHS OF INDELIBILITY

Abstract:

The paper is an attempt to analyse the operability and impact of memory, and post memory on individual lives set in situations and spaces suffused with the trauma and violence from the past. The essay is divided into a quartet. The first section introduces the intent of the analysis based on the literary work chosen for study. The second part focuses on a legend that has a lasting presence. The third section of the article examines the transmission of memory and post memory across generations. The fourth part is the conclusion, summing up the analysis of whether indelibility vis-à-vis memory is eternal or ephemeral.

Key words: Collective memory, post memory, intersectionality, indelibility, consanguinity.

Introduction

Efficacy in dealing with egregious episodes in life involves the effacement of moments in Gehenna. But unfortunately for some individuals such junctures of oppression manifest as the juggernaut jeopardizing their present with painful paroxysms from the past. The reiterative recollection and retention of the traumatic past across generations, moulds memory into a mammoth legacy instead of an ephemeral entity. This article shall explore aspects of violence and trauma through the prism of memory and post-memory as portrayed by Eka Kurniawan's novel *Beauty is a Wound*. The loci of focus shall be – the significance of storytelling as a

conduit to construct and conserve memories that are intergenerational, the imprint of traumatic experiences on memory, inheritability as an integral ingredient of post-memory, the prepotency of memory in the ideation of identities and the construction of memories in the crucible of socio-cultural and historical transactions. The theoretical tools to interpret topics of consideration shall be theories on collective memory by Maurice Halbwachs, post-memory by Marianne Hirsch along with intersectionality. The gynocentricity of the fictional text chosen for reference lends itself to evaluating the intractability of intersections of gender, race, class and colonialism. Hence the particularities and peculiarities inherent in the multitudes of memory offer a basis for delving into the depths of indelible impressions on individuals vis-à-vis consanguinity.

The Lasting Longevity of Lore

In the novel *Beauty is a Wound*, the genesis of the geographical locale – Halimunda in Indonesia is steeped in a surviving story. The legend of Princess Rengganis. The breathtaking beauty was “...the last descendant of the Pajajaran royal bloodline, who had inherited the loveliness of all the princesses in the Pakuan Kingdom” (Kurniawan, 114). Her father was the last monarch of the kingdom before its sovereignty ceased, enslaving it to the Dutch conquest. The pulchritude of Princess Rengganis infused pain into her life and those of her loved ones. Paternal pride was diminished by his desire for his own daughter. “His feelings of desire and impropriety clashed and gnawed away everything inside him, until he came to think only death could free him from his suffering” (Kurniawan, 115). Her mother was so enraged at the prospect of none other than their own daughter endangering their conjugal relationship, that she braced herself to stab her daughter to death. “But every time she saw her daughter, even she would be charmed and fall in love, and forget all about her murderous intent” (Kurniawan, 115). The incredible beauty that Rengganis was blessed with, disallowed the blossoming of her life and rendered it barren.

People said that the princess herself had realized that her beauty brought misfortune.

When she was still a child and free to wander outside the palace walls, she caused turmoil and disruptions, big and small. Wherever she went people would gaze at her face, shrouded in a thin mist of melancholy, with blank idiotic stares. Frozen like absurd human statues, only their eyeballs moved, following her every step. Her appearances caused the civil servants to daydream and neglect state affairs, so that swathes of the kingdom were captured by bands of robbers before they could be reclaimed at great effort and cost, sacrificing the lives of half the royal army.

(Kurniawan, 115).

Leading a life of self-imposed seclusion, the pretty princess' only contact with the world outside was through an aperture in the shut door. It was through this crevice that her maids provided her with attires and victuals. When her parents, the king and the queen could no longer keep the lid on their forbidden feelings towards their child, they decided that the only solution was to get her married. They despatched ninety- nine messengers to the farthest corners of their territory, to the neighbouring nations to herald a contest for princes and knights. "The first prize was the right to marry the most beautiful woman in the world, Princess Rengganis" (Kurniawan, 116). The contest commenced with the arrival of handsome contestants who were asked to describe the ideal woman. "The King promised that if the man wanted someone exactly like the Princess and the Princess wanted someone exactly like the man in front of her door, then they could marry" (Kurniawan, 116). This endeavour proved to be nugatory. As a result, the unsuccessful princes waged war on the kingdom to take away the princess by force. The terror that the war unleashed on the subjects earned "Halimunda's goddess of beauty", the epithet "terrorizing beauty" (Kurniawan, 117). "The curse of beauty became even more

extreme: thousands of soldiers were wounded and dead, the whole nation was in ruins, sickness and starvation struck without mercy, and all of this was thanks to that infernal beauty” (Kurniawan, 117).

The distraught princess decided that to put the kibosh on war she had to get married right away. Rengganis vowed to marry the first person who appeared before her window. She had in the meantime confined herself to a dimly lit room with only an oil lamp and had sewn a dazzling wedding dress. Attired in it her effulgent beauty shone unparalleled. But on opening the long-shuttered window, she found none outside except a dog. The princess in her wedding finery came to her groom – the dog and impervious to what people said, she married him. “Because, ... a dog could not care less whether I am beautiful or not” (Kurniawan, 122). Since her wedding to a canine would not be accepted, the story goes that the newlyweds retreated to “...a foggy forest at the edge of the South Seas. It was the princess herself who named it Halimunda, The Land of Fog. They lived there for many years, and of course had children. Most of the people who lived in Halimunda believed they were the descendants of the Princess and that dog, whose name nobody knew” (Kurniawan, 122).

The saga of Rengganis springs a surprise wherein, the most coveted trait – beauty – specifically feminine kawaii-ness is perceived as a bane and not a boon. The hapless princess finds herself at the intersection of gender roles. Being a daughter, her filial fidelity must ensure that she upholds the dignity of the royal household. As the princess, she must be sensitive to the struggles of her subjects wrought by her badgering beauty. Being an individual who gives in to the social perception of her stunning beauty as an embrangement, Rengganis clearly has no qualms about acquiescing to the others’ appraisal of her as the femme fatale. She has internalised Charles Horton Cooley’s “The looking-glass self: I am not what I think I am, and I am not what you think I am. I am what I think you think I am.”

The dysphoric story of the unfortunate princess was emblazoned on the collective memory of the society and it was often narrated as a legend. It was thus that Maman Gendeng – the invincible warrior who had been dejected with his unrequited love, heard the story. His resolve to marry the princess with resplendent beauty, impels him to embark on a journey to Halimunda hundreds of miles away. On enquiring about the place where he could meet Rengganis he is asked, “Which Rengganis? Tons of ladies go by that name. Even streets and rivers are named Rengganis” (Kurniawan, 120). Gendeng is stupefied to discover that she had died “hundreds of years ago”. Yet her presence in the form of her story was an integral part of the landscape. Maurice Halbwachs states that “...a society can have a collective memory. It refers to the shared pool of memories, knowledge and information of a social group” (Halbwachs). Thus, his arrival in Halimunda can be seen as an implacement into a physical setting that breathed and continued to breathe the story of Rengganis making it an intergenerational inheritance.

Of Turbulence and Tenebric Trauma

The fictional landscape of *Beauty is a Wound* has woven into its tapestry, the turbulent times of Dutch and Japanese colonial occupation, the ruthlessness of guerilla warfare and reciprocal bloody military executions, the rise and fall of communism and macabre massacres. In spine-chilling supplementarity to the hellacious historical happenings, the fishing port of Halimunda where the narrative of the novel is chiefly centred, has a genealogy of hazardous fortune ingrained into its existence like its foundress, the unfortunate Princess Rengganis. Thus the collective memory of Halimunda emanates from its corporality, inherited and inheritable allure of beauty that thrusts its possessor to live with the anguish of beauty and its concomitant catastrophes.

The narrative of the novel begins with the description of a poltergeist phenomenon. Dewi Ayu dead for twenty-one years, rises from her grave on an afternoon and walks through the

vacant streets of Halimunda covered only with the shroud she had been wrapped in, while being interred. The inhabitants scurry for cover and watch the scary spectacle in awe. Dewi Ayu “the most well-respected prostitute” (Kurniawan, 219) in Halimunda heads towards her home. It is the memory of trauma that burns alive in her and impels her to shun the serenity of the sepulchre, returning to a malefic world. Marianne Hirsch explains that:

Trauma in its literal meaning is a wound inflicted on the flesh. Roberta Culbertson stresses that “no experience is more one’s own than harm to one’s own skin... The wound inflicted on the skin can be read as a sign of trauma’s incommunicability, a figure for the traumatic real that defines a seemingly unbridgeable gap between survivors and their descendants (80).

Born out of an incestuous relationship, abandoned by her parents at her grandparents’ doorstep, Dewi Ayu grows up to be a ravishing beauty under the care of her Dutch plantation owner grandfather, Ted Stammler and grandmother Marietje. She is educated by the best teachers at the Franciscan school. The nuns “were impressed by her natural intelligence, but worried by her beauty, and a number of nuns tried to persuade her to take vows of poverty, purity and chastity” (Kurniawan, 41). When the war broke out in Europe and the Japanese occupation of Halimunda seemed imminent, her grandfather was ordered to join the war against the Japanese. With the Dutch losing their battle against the Japanese, the families of the Dutch residents were being asked to evacuate. But Dewi Ayu was resolute in her decision to stay back, reiterating that she would remain at the place that was her home and wait for her grandfather’s return from war. Ted Stammler does not survive the war. The Japanese gather all the Dutch women and children, bundle them up into crowded trucks and take them as prisoners of war to “Bloedenkamp, a prison with a bloody history” (Kurniawan, 63). The prisoners are coerced to live in squalid cells infested with sewer rats, cockroaches, lizards, geckos and leeches. Starving

with little or no food they are forced into doing hard labour at the prison. Pushed to the wall for survival, the five thousand prisoners all women and children, fall sick and without any medical care start dying. “Babies started to die, and then the old people. Sickness also killed young mothers, children, young girls – anyone might die at any moment. The field behind the cells turned into cemetery” (Kurniawan, 68).

When her friend Ola’s mother is dying, she forces the fearful Ola to approach the Japanese commandant to seek medicine. Ola returns without the medicine because the commandant would give it only if she slept with him. Dewi Ayu goes to the commandant and tells him that she would take Ola’s place if he gave Ola’s mother medicine and a doctor. The man ravages her body and Dewi Ayu goes to the cell with a doctor to check on Ola’s mother and the doctor pronounces that the woman is dead already. After two years of pestilent existence at the prison, the Japanese separated all women aged between seventeen and twenty-eight and finally chose twenty girls – “These chosen girls – young, pretty, healthy, and strong...” (Kurniawan, 75). They are taken to Mama Kalong’s whorehouse in Halimunda to work as prostitutes to service the Japanese military officers. Every night the place was filled with hysterical screaming when the girls were raped, “a number of the girls even succeeded in running out into the hall stark naked, before the soldiers recaptured them and threw them back on top of their beds... That night they were taken by four or five men each” ((Kurniawan, 88). The girls were given new names after flowers – Rose, Orchid, Dahlia, Alamanda. Dewi Ayu gets pregnant and gives birth to her first child whom she names Alamanda. A visit by the Japanese General Musashi puts an end to their excruciating existence as whores.

Though saved from continued prostitution, the trauma borne by their bodies, the memories of being molested are so inscribed on their skin harmed beyond redemption, that the girls struggle to find themselves an identity that seems elusive. They are at a loss as to what they would tell their mothers. They stand before the mirror, trying to acquire courage, saying to their

images, “Mama, now I am a whore.” Of course they couldn’t say it like that, so they would try again, “Mama, I used to be a whore.” But that also sounded wrong, so they would say, “Mama, I was forced into prostitution” (Kurniawan, 95). When the war ended and the girls and their families were to board a flight that would take them to Europe, Dewi Ayu refused to leave Halimunda. She is steadfast in her decision and asserts, “ But this is my home. She had already told Mama Kalong that she didn’t want to leave Halimunda. She would remain in the city, even if it meant she had to be a prostitute” (Kurniawan,100).

In Consanguinous Custody of Post memory

Dewi Ayu takes a loan from Mama Kalong to buy back her home that had been occupied by a native family. She tries to retrieve the jewellery she had buried in the sewer pipes of her home, to repay the loan. Unfortunately, she fails to find her hidden treasure and goes back to whoring to return the money she loaned and for her livelihood. She gives birth to three daughters, working as a prostitute – Alamanda, Adinda and Maya Dewi. She tries her best to kill her fourth child in her womb but fails. Her three daughters are ravishingly beautiful and she fears that they might meet the same fate as hers. So she fervently prays that her fourth child is born ugly. Her prayers are answered when the child is born ugly, “...like a cursed monster from hell” (Kurniawan, 4). Dewi Ayu does not look at her child but asks if the child is pretty and since those present don’t reveal the truth about the hideous-faced baby, she ironically names it Beauty and remarks “There’s no curse more terrible than to give birth to a pretty female in a world of men as nasty as dogs in heat” (Kurniawan, 5). Dewi Ayu covers herself with a shroud and lies down to die. She decides to terminate her life, to put an end to the cycle of life that she had begun by giving birth to four daughters. Her three older daughters had by then begun their own lives.

The three daughters of Dewi Ayu lead their lives in the city of Halimunda, that is a storehouse of collective memory. Commenting on the importance of the place where memories from the past dynamically intersperse with individual lives in the present, Maurice Halbwachs explains that:

...impressions rush by, one after another, and leave nothing behind in the mind, we can understand how we recapture the past only by understanding how it is, in effect, preserved by our physical surroundings. It is to space - the space we occupy, traverse, have continual access to, or can at any time reconstruct in thought and imagination ... Thus, every collective memory unfolds within a spatial framework.

Now space is a reality that endures: (6,7).

The significant specificity with which space plays a pivotal role in oppression is succinctly stated by Patrick R. Granzka – “Oppression has not only a when, but a where...this includes the ways in which the particulars of landscapes and geographies create sites of oppression...that are inextricable from racial, class, gender, and sexual dynamics” (99).

Accordingly, Dewi Ayu’s three daughters who have inherited their mother’s coruscating beauty are unknowingly captives in their geographical location Halimunda and its allegiance to past memories. The girls live in an intersectional labyrinth where a multiplicity of factors transmitted to them intergenerationally underlines their interpellation. Their beauty has a Dutch lineage that places them in a class apart from the natives in terms of their race. Their class and gender in terms of their mother’s vocation as a whore, consigns them into a space of vulnerability. The fourth daughter beauty with her loathsome visage is more susceptible to societal oppression, being a social outcast.

Their consanguinity chooses their physical and psychological realm to experience the domino effects of post-memory.

The particular relation to a parental past described, evoked, and analysed... has come to be seen as a syndrome of belatedness or “post-ness” and has been variously termed “absent memory”(Ellen Fine), “inherited memory”, “belated memory”, (Celia Lury, Alison Landsberg), “received history” (James Young), “haunting legacy” (Gabriele Schwab) and “postmemory” (Hirsch, 3).

The testimony to the functioning of postmemory is evident when despite Dewi Ayu’s best efforts in securing a better future for her children, the eldest daughter Alamanda is drugged and molested by the chief officer of Halimunda military district. Violated against her will Alamanda cannot go against her conscience and marry her lover Kliwon. She marries her molester and to seek revenge and wears a metal undergarment. But ends up being brutalised more. Alamanda’s act of wearing a metal undergarment to make herself inviolable is an indication that the memory of her mother’s violability as a whore is alive and she tries her best to avoid the same fate but fails miserably in safeguarding the sanctity of her body. The second daughter Adinda’s son Krisan inherits his father’s womanising ways. He rapes his simpleminded yet stunningly gorgeous cousin Rengganis the beautiful in the school washroom. When the girl gets pregnant and asks him what should she tell her parents, the youth asks her to state that she had been raped by a dog. From the legend of Princess Rengganis who married a dog to Rengganis the beautiful, the granddaughter of Dewi Ayu and daughter of her third daughter Maya Dewi, life comes full circle. Beauty in spite of her invisibility to the world for her abominable ugliness, gets pregnant. Her consensual relationship in secrecy is with her nephew Krisan, her second sister Adinda’s son, without even knowing his identity. Elaborating

on the potency of “rememory” Marianne Hirsch , asserts that “ The “re” in “rememory” signals not just the threat, but the certainty of repetition: “it will happen again” (84).

Conclusion

The novel *Beauty is a Wound* portrays the paradoxical puissance of beauty, drawing our attention to the plethora of particularities like the impactful intrusion of memory and post-memory into the present. The performative dexterity of collective memory vis-à-vis a geographical locale is apparently endemic. The operability of inheritable traumatic experiences is to an extent beyond the agency of the individual. However, the deliberate and conscious attempt to alter and realign the configuration of the interacting intersecting factors is indubitably agentic. Therefore though external factors impede the identity of an individual, the plurality of identity offers ample opportunities to seek, mould, restore and establish our identities aligned with individual predilection. There is nothing as pliable and equally rigid as the human mind. Indefatigability is indubitably the key to efficaciously efface the inimical and indelible stranglehold of memories.

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